

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK MOTIVATION AND WORK EXPERIENCE WITH THE PERFORMANCE OF THE HEAD STATE BASIC SCHOOL IN BEKASI

by Abdul Khalis Razak

Submission date: 12-Nov-2019 01:22AM (UTC-0800)

Submission ID: 1212151368

File name: RELATIONSHIP_-_Pak_Mul.pdf (246.62K)

Word count: 3132

Character count: 17537

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK MOTIVATION AND WORK EXPERIENCE WITH THE PERFORMANCE OF THE HEAD STATE BASIC SCHOOL IN BEKASI

Abdul Khalis Razak¹, Mulyadi Mulyadi²

Ph.D Student Islamic University of Jakarta¹, Indonesia, Islamic University of Jakarta, Indonesia²

¹abdul.khalis2016@gmail.com, ²Mul_amir07@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This research aims at achieving a sound understanding on the relationship between principals' work motivation and work experience both individually or simultaneously with their performance. The hypotheses are: (1) There is a positive correlation between principals' work motivation and their performance, (2) there is a positive correlation between principals' work experience and their performance, (3) Simultaneously there is a positive correlation between principals' work motivation, work experience and their performance. Survey with correlational technique was used as research method. The sample are 53 teachers chosen by proportional random sampling technique from Public Elementary Schools in Bekasi City. The simple and multiple correlation and regression are used as a tool for analysis. The research findings are as follow:

First, principals' work motivation has a positive correlation with their performance, with significant coefficient correlation $r_{y1} = 0.447$ at one sided 0.05 alpha level. Work motivation shares 20% on variation in principals' performance through significant regression equation $\hat{Y} = 68.37 + 0.21X_1$ at 0.05 alpha level.

Second, principals' work experience has a positive correlation with their performance with significant correlation coefficient $r_{y1} = 0.337$ at one sided 0.05 alpha level. Work experience shares 11.4% on the variation in principals' performance through a significant regression equation $\hat{Y} = 50.50 + 0.34X_2$ at 0.05 alpha level.

Third, simultaneously principals' work motivation and work experience have a positive correlation with their performance with significant correlation coefficient $R_{y.12} = 0.521$ at one sided 0.05 alpha level. Both variables share 27,1% on variation in principals' performance through significant regression equation $\hat{Y} = 43.10 + 0.19X_1 + 0.27X_2$ at 0.05 alpha level.

These findings can be used as input to enhance principals' performance through improvement of reward system that encourage their work motivation and of human resources development that encourage their work experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

According to Mulyasa, headmasters in Indonesia cannot yet be regarded as professional managers, because his appointment is not based on professional abilities and education, but on his experience as a teacher. The World Bank (1999) once indicated that one of the reasons for the declining quality of schooling education in Indonesia was the lack of professionalism of school principals as education managers at the field level.

In terms of the leadership of the principal, according to Suyatno, principals have broad autonomy so they must be brave enough to make decisions more autonomously by using a participatory leadership style. In such participatory decision making the principal needs to involve all components of the school community: teachers, students, principals, employees, parents of

students, and the community functionally. This means that the elements of the school community are given opportunities and are invited to think about the progress of the school and improve the quality of the school through their respective contributions in accordance with their capacity. Educators who are in school really determine the change in the school itself towards better and better quality.

To streamline the leadership of the school head of the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education Ministry of Education establishes a number of functional roles of principals, known as EMASLIM, which include the role of the principal as: (1) educator / educator, (2) manager / manager (3) administrator / administrator (4) supervisor / supervisor, (5) leader / leader, (6) innovator / reformer, and (7) motivator / interest generator. The functional role is then translated into an indicator for the principal's performance

evaluation. With this measurable performance, it is expected that the principal will manage all of his school's resources in achieving educational goals.

B. Limiting Problems and Formulating Problems

In this study the problem is limited to:

1. The relationship between work motivation and the performance of the principal;
2. The relationship between work experience and the performance of the principal;
3. The relationship between work motivation and work experience together with the performance of the principal.

While the formulation of the problem is:

1. Is there a relationship between work motivation and the performance of the head of an elementary school in Bekasi City?
2. Is there a relationship between work experience and the performance of the head of the Elementary School in Bekasi City?
3. Is there a relationship between work motivation and work experience together with the performance of the head of the Primary School in Bekasi City?

II. Research Theory Study

1. Principal's Performance

a. Conceptual definition

Conceptually what is meant by the performance of the principal is the measurable input, process, and results of the implementation of the roles and functions of the principal as educators, managers, administrators, supervisors, leaders, innovators and motivators.

b. Operational definition

Operationally the principal's performance is the teacher's assessment of the principal's performance in carrying out his main duties as the principal, namely (1) educator, (2) manager, (3) administrator, (4) supervisor, (5) leader, (6) innovators, and (7) motivators.

III. Research methodology

A. Research Objectives

This research focused on the performance of the principal in a Public Elementary School in the City of Bekasi. The performance of the Principal is related to other variables taken from the characteristics of the principal, namely work motivation and work experience.

Operationally this research is carried out in order to obtain empirical images regarding:

1. The relationship between work motivation and the performance of the principal;

2. Relationship to work experience with school principals' performance

3. Relationship between work motivation and work experience with the performance of the principal

B. Place and Time of Research

This research was conducted within the National Education Office of the City of Bekasi, West Java. This research was conducted for 5 months.

C. The method

In the study is the survey research method. Data retrieval is done randomly or randomly at State Elementary Schools, each village in West and East Bekasi. The survey method is research taking samples from the population by using a questionnaire as a basic data collection tool. Survey methods can be used to test hypotheses regarding the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. In this study the dependent variable is the performance of the principal (Y), while the independent variables are work motivation (X1) and work experience (X2).

D. Population and Samples

The population in this study were all elementary school principals in the city of Bekasi which amounted to 520 people while the sample was taken as many as 60 people, namely 11.53%.

E. Data Collection Techniques

This data is collected through research instruments, namely the principal's performance instrument, the principal's work motivation instrument and the instrument's work experience of the principal. The instrument after being tested to produce validity and reliability. The instrument was only used as a data collector.

F. Inferential statistics are used to test research hypotheses using moment product correlation and simple and multiple regression. Testing the significance of the correlation coefficient using the t test for simple correlation and F test for multiple correlations. Before testing hypotheses, analysis prerequisites are tested first, namely testing for normality and linearity. Normality testing was performed on the estimated standard error using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. While the regression linearity testing of the dependent variable on the independent variable is done by simple regression analysis.

G. Statistical Hypothesis

Based on the research hypothesis stated in the previous chapter, the research statistics hypothesis is stated as follows:

1. $H_0: \rho_{y1} = 0$ $H_1: \rho_{y1} > 0$

2. $H_0: \rho_{y2} = 0$ $H_1: \rho_{y2} > 0$

3. $H_0: \rho_{y12} = 0$ $H_1: \rho_{y12} > 0$

Where :

ρ_1 = Simple correlation coefficient between work motivation and the performance of the principal

ρ_2 = Simple correlation coefficient between work experience and the performance of the principal

ρ_{12} = Multiple correlation coefficients between work motivation and work experience with the performance of the principal.

a. Conceptual definition

Conceptually, what is meant by the principal's work motivation is the value of expectation, instrumentality, and valence of the job as the principal who encourages him to mobilize all his abilities in his work.

b. Operational definition

Operationally, what is meant by the principal's work motivation is a score for the assessment of

IV. RESEARCH RESULT

1. Motivation of Principal Work

1. The relationship between work motivation and the performance of the principal

From the operational definition of the principal's work performance and work motivation and work discipline, the principal is made a questionnaire and after being tested for validity and reliability, the contribution of work motivation to the principal's performance is significantly positively related. The results of this study are in line with the findings of previous research, as discussed in the following section.

First, the relationship between work motivation and the performance of the principal. In this study, it turns out that the two variables are positively related significantly, therefore any increase in the principal's work motivation will be followed linearly by improving his performance, and vice versa, any decrease in the principal's work motivation will be followed linearly by a decrease in his performance.

This shows the importance of work motivation in the perspective of expectation theory as a predictor for the performance of principals. In accordance with the theory of hope, the high and low level of effort devoted by a school principal in work, is determined by his expectation that his

the principal's work motivation, which measures:

(1) The expectancy component is how much the principal hopes that the effort he or she is carrying out in an opportunity produces good performance.

(2) Components of instrumentality, namely how much the principal believes that good performance has the opportunity to generate rewards, which include, (a) material rewards, (b) non-material rewards, (c) immaterial rewards. (3)

The valence component, which is how high the school principal evaluates or his dream of the three types of rewards he will receive.

2. Principal Work Experience

a. Conceptual definition

Conceptually, what is meant by the principal's work experience is the length of work of the principal who starts from the beginning of his working period, that is, since they are accepted as educators or teachers to become school principals.

b. Operational definition

Operationally what is meant by the work experience of the principal is the work period score of the principal (in the year) starting from the beginning of his career until now (when carried out research) being the principal

business will produce performance (expectation value), and that his performance will be rewarded (instrumental value), and that the reward is valuable (valence value)) Rewards here include material benefits such as salary, allowances, pensions; non-material rewards such as promotions, promotions, award certificates; and immaterial rewards such as inner satisfaction and meaningful feelings as the principal.

The existence of a positive relationship between work motivation of principals and their performance in this study is in line with the findings of Johnson, Spuck and Lortie that extrinsic motivation in the form of material and non-material rewards and intrinsic motivation in the form of immaterial rewards turned out to increase work motivation while work motivation encourages participation in achieving school goals .

2. Relationship between Work Experience and Principal Performance

Second, the relationship between work experience and the performance of the principal. The two variables turned out to be positively related because each increase in work experience would be followed by an increase in the performance of the principal, and vice versa any decrease in work experience would be followed by a decrease in the performance of the principal.

This finding shows the importance of the principal's work experience variable as a predictor for the performance of the principal. The work experience of the principal in this study was measured from the current period of work, types of positions, and previous experience at school. The results of this study are in line with the findings of Manulang who argue that experienced people will be smarter than those who have absolutely no experience. This opinion was also supported by Jakoeb Hidayat and Koesyono who stated: "Work experience (and explicitly including work training) with working period indicators / age of workers provides evidence that all levels of education, the average income increases according to the age group".

13

3. Relationship between Work Motivation and Work Experience Together with Principal Performance

Third, the relationship between work motivation and work experience together with the performance of the principal. Individually each of the two variables is positively related to the performance of the principal, and together they are also positively related to the performance of the principal.

This study shows that although the average work motivation score of principals is only included in the high category because the mean is equivalent to 81.51% the highest possible score, while work experience is also included in the high category because the mean is equivalent to 80.52% chance highest score. However, if compared to each partial correlation with the principal's performance, it turns out that work motivation is a better predictor of work experience.

This means that for the population of the head of a public elementary school in Bekasi, the main problem in improving the performance of the principal is not an increase in work experience but an increase in the work motivation of the principal itself. By increasing the increase in work motivation from the high category to the very high category, the performance of principals will increase even higher. In line with the theory of hope, the increase in work motivation must certainly be done by giving rewards that he believes he will receive more valuable in the view of the principal.

V. Conclusion

The results of this study contain the theoretical and practical implications as follows:

First, theoretically the higher the work motivation of the principal is the higher the performance and conversely the lower the work motivation of the principal is the lower the performance. Therefore,

practically, to improve the performance of the principal can be traveled by increasing his work motivation. In accordance with the theory of expectation, the work motivation factors that need to be improved include the expectation value, instrumentality and valence of the job as the principal. A principal will exert all his efforts to produce the best performance, if he has great expectations that his business will truly produce performance (expectation value), and that his performance will truly be rewarded (instrumental value), and that the reward is true really valuable to him (valence value).

The first factor, which is the belief that the business really produces the expected performance, can be improved by providing training related to the implementation of the main tasks as the task of the principal. The trainings will produce the knowledge, attitudes, and skills needed in the implementation of basic work to produce the desired performance. In addition, facilities and infrastructure also need to be provided that allow the principal to carry out the main work as well as possible.

The second factor is the principal's belief that his performance will be rewarded, can be increased by using a performance-based reward system. As other state employees the rewards received by the principal are not sufficiently stimulating, because the amount and amount are the same between those who perform well and those who perform poorly. With the existence of a fair performance system which means that it is based on performance, the principal will be motivated to work better.

Third, the belief factor that valuable rewards in the school principal's view can be increased by increasing the attractiveness of all types of rewards that might be given. If in the form of material rewards, the form and base may be increased, such as basic salary, bonuses, incentives, or benefits that are more sufficient to fulfill basic needs. Non-material rewards can also be made more interesting, for example the acceleration of promotion, promotion of structural positions, or the awarding of special awards. For immaterial rewards such as satisfaction, feeling meaningful, they may be subjective but can also be enhanced by increasing noble values by attaching noble values in the profession as the principal. Second, theoretically the higher the work experience of the principal is the higher the performance and conversely the lower the work experience of the principal is the lower the performance. Therefore to improve the performance of principals in a practical way can be achieved by increasing the tenure of the office and

providing experience in other fields in the form of conceptual, technical and interpersonal skills as managers.

The first factor, work experience can be improved by increasing the principal's insight into conceptual issues related to their main tasks.

The second factor, work experience in the form of technical skills can be improved by providing technical training related to the principal's principal duties as manager, which includes the preparation of school programs, preparation of school personnel, empowerment of education staff and utilizing school resources.

The third factor, work experience in the form of interpersonal skills can be improved by providing emotional intelligence or social intelligence training and applying it in its main tasks as a manager. .

Third, theoretically the higher the work motivation and work experience of the principal is the higher the performance and conversely the lower the

work motivation and work experience of the principal is the lower the performance. Simultaneously, the two variables contribute greatly to improving the performance of principals and therefore both should be improved simultaneously so as to have a greater effect on improving performance.

Thus, when given treatment in the form of increased work experience, for example in the form of training of managerial managerial skills, it should be accompanied by a policy of increasing rewards that will stimulate the work motivation of the principal to carry out the results. Likewise, when a performance-based reward system policy is implemented, it should also be accompanied by work experience that will allow the principal to get the desired reward. In this way, principals will be highly motivated as well as reliable work experience to produce the expected performance from them.

DAFTAR PUSTAKA

Agor, WH. 1986 "the Logic of Intuition" How to Executives Make Important Decisions". *Organizational Dynamics*, 14 (3), hal 5-18

Ali, Muhammad, 1994. *Pengembangan dan Filosofi kepemimpinan Kerja*. Jakarta: Bharata.

Ary, D; Jacobs, LC; Razaviech, A. 1985. *Pengantar Penelitian dalam Pendidikan*. Penerjemah A Furchan. Surabaya: Usaha Nasional.

Atkinson, RL, dkk, 1993. *Pengantar Psikologi*. Penerjemah M. Taufik. Jakarta: Erlangga.

Bass, BM. 1990. *Handbook of Leadership*: A

Survey of Theory and Research. New York: Free Press.

Katz, RL. 1955. "Skills of An Effective Administrators". *Harvard Business Review*, January-February, hal 33-42.

McCall, MW & Lambardo, MM. 1983. "What Makes a Top Executive?" *Psychology oday*, February, hal 26-31.

Michel, TR, Wabba, MA & House, RJ. 1974.

"Expectancy Theory in Work Motivation: Logical and Methodological Issues", *Human Relations*, 27(2), hal 121-147.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK MOTIVATION AND WORK EXPERIENCE WITH THE PERFORMANCE OF THE HEAD STATE BASIC SCHOOL IN BEKASI

ORIGINALITY REPORT

14%

SIMILARITY INDEX

4%

INTERNET SOURCES

3%

PUBLICATIONS

13%

STUDENT PAPERS

PRIMARY SOURCES

1

Submitted to Universitas Negeri Jakarta

Student Paper

2%

2

Submitted to University of Derby

Student Paper

2%

3

Submitted to UC, Irvine

Student Paper

1%

4

www.scribd.com

Internet Source

1%

5

ByeolBee Um, HyunGyung Joo, DaYeon Her. "The Relationship between Elementary School Teachers' Work Motivation and Well-Being: The Mediating Effects of Principal Leadership and Work Stress", International Journal of Social Science Studies, 2018

Publication

1%

6

Submitted to School of Business and Management ITB

Student Paper

1%

7	Submitted to Universitas Negeri Semarang Student Paper	1%
8	Submitted to University of Sydney Student Paper	1%
9	Submitted to London School of Economics and Political Science Student Paper	1%
10	Submitted to University of Southampton Student Paper	<1%
11	digilib.unimed.ac.id Internet Source	<1%
12	Submitted to Peking University Shenzhen Graduate School Student Paper	<1%
13	Submitted to Universitas Jenderal Achmad Yani Student Paper	<1%
14	Submitted to Central Queensland University Student Paper	<1%
15	digilib.unila.ac.id Internet Source	<1%
16	Submitted to Universitas Diponegoro Student Paper	<1%
17	Submitted to Grand Canyon University Student Paper	<1%

18

Submitted to Higher Education Commission
Pakistan

Student Paper

<1%

19

Submitted to Edge Hill College of Higher
Education

Student Paper

<1%

20

"The Effect of Participative Leadership of
Principal of Private School on Work Motivation
of Teacher and their Performance in Tangerang
City", International Journal of Engineering and
Advanced Technology, 2019

Publication

<1%

Exclude quotes Off

Exclude matches Off

Exclude bibliography On

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK MOTIVATION AND WORK EXPERIENCE WITH THE PERFORMANCE OF THE HEAD STATE BASIC SCHOOL IN BEKASI

GRADEMARK REPORT

FINAL GRADE

/0

GENERAL COMMENTS

Instructor

PAGE 1

PAGE 2

PAGE 3

PAGE 4

PAGE 5
